

INTERACTION MODALITIES WITH FOOD: PROPOSAL OF A NEW DESIGN METHOD. ANALYSIS ON CHOCOLATE PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

Food is becoming a design material: is no longer of interest only to cooks and pastry chef but also to designers. The design of the new "material-food" creates new sensory worlds: as a result, the taste is analysed as a new and unexpected experience. Moreover food handling is a key aspect that is acquiring more and more importance because it is very important in the design process of a food product to know which are the ways and the places of interaction and consume between food and consumer.

Interactions modes with food are changing according to its "usage context" and its presentation form (extruded, expanded, sandwich, mesh, granules, etc.). These presentation forms are directly linked to food ingredients and are often mediated by the presence of a packaging, which determines the user's first interaction with the food. An example is given by a study of a chocolate bar that is illustrated in this paper.

Keywords: *Chocolate, Methodological Approach to Design, Interaction analysis, User interaction modes, Materials*

INTRODUCTION

The research field is food design, where the food is considered as material for the project, by means of which chefs and food designers experiment and search for new tasting journeys, while enhancing the sensorial perceptions of the user-consumer (Meroni and Simeoni, 2009).

The paper illustrates a specific case-study, chocolate, documenting new design approach, for the material-chocolate, capable not only of enhancing its taste, but also of simplifying its handling and consumption.

Chocolate can be identified as one of the typical products of the Piedmont region and has been the subject of several design researches at the Politecnico di Torino (Padovani, 2010).

The analysis of the different types of chocolate available on the market (chocolates, bars, eggs etc.) has led to the choice of a specific product category, the chocolate bars, often undervalued, being very common, but today very widespread and growing in the market (new tastes, new formats, new colours). A further study into the world of chocolate bars and their variants has enabled the investigation of the existing relationships and reciprocities between types, tastes, ingredients, dimensions, formats, production processes. In this way it was possible to define, for each type of chocolate bar, the most suitable consumption modalities for a planned interaction, which, however, not only considers the food and the consumer, but also takes into account, the packaging, focusing on the structure and materials that wrap the food product and it should be considered as its first ingredient (Allione, De Giorgi and Lerma, 2011). The research object, through the analysis of all the protagonists involved in the interaction, is to define an innovative design system for the creation of a chocolate bar that can be savoured and tasted at its best.

BACKGROUND ANALYSIS

Before going into the details of this research, it is necessary to make a brief digression into the world of chocolate starting with its production process.

It involves a very long and delicate process, starting with the harvesting of the pods containing the cocoa beans, this stage takes place in countries situated in the equatorial zones. Once harvested, the beans will undergo numerous production processes before becoming chocolate (Perera, 2008).

The chocolate is available in three basic tastes: white, milk and dark to which additional ingredients may be added thus obtaining new flavours and fillings (Gioffrè, 2003).

The formats available are bars, chocolates, creams, snacks and other sizes such as ice creams, puddings, etc. Among these the bar is the most purchased, both dark and milk, representing the sector of the chocolate universe experiencing the greatest growth, both in volume and value, with a sales percentage of 50% (Amadori, 2002), in Italy. And yet, the chocolate bar is often undervalued nowadays. Indeed, it is not considered a gift item, as happens in the case of chocolates, creams, Easter eggs, since it is often associated with individual consumption or for cooking. However, it is important to underline how the new tastes developed have led to the planning of new shapes and formats of the bars, which, seen from a different perspective, may be compared to a box of chocolates. It is sufficient to think of any filled bar: at the moment when the individual squares are broken off and thus shared, many little chocolates are obtained, each with its own filling (Guixé, 2010). On the basis of a detailed analysis of 40 bars available on the market it is possible to identify different classifications or methods of interpreting a chocolate bar, based on:

- format, relating to the dimensions of the bar, distinguishable in mini, standard and maxi.
- portion, subdivided into single and multi-portion.
- form, distinguishable into simple and complex. The first type present in the collective imagination is composed of typical squares, easily broken off (through “invitations”), while in the second type more space is awarded to creativity and design.
- breaking off, which can be regular or irregular according to the presence or not of invitations-grooves.
- taste, that determines the classification of the bars into classic, flavoured, with filled pieces; the latter ones are further subdivided into liquid, soft and hard fillings.

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH: ANALYSIS OF INTERACTION

Once the subject of the study, the chocolate bar, was

identified, the research then moved on the analysis of the interactions that involve this product, by examining, firstly, the protagonists, that are: the user, the packaging and the chocolate bar itself and then by identifying the relationships that can be determined between these protagonists.

THE PROTAGONISTS OF THE INTERACTION

Entering into further details, it is possible to identify three principal players that come into play in the investigated interaction: that is, the chocolate bar, the consumer and the packaging (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Analysis of interaction scheme

User-consumer

The user chooses to consume the chocolate for different reasons: physiological and psychological (Langham, 2003). From the physiological perspective the chocolate is capable of stimulating the production of serotonin, while determining an improvement in humour; from the psychological viewpoint, on the other hand, chocolate consumption can be associated with particular situations, such as festivities, anniversaries, moments of self-gratification or consolation, thereby assuming a positive value. Four types of consumers can be distinguished:

- the tasters, that is, those who look at chocolate with a scientific approach, not governed by instinct, but by rationality; they know how to consider the food in all its parts and choose the right chocolate for the appropriate moment. Consumption is often

connected with a tasting and a training course (Caraceni, 2010).

- the cultured ones, for whom consumption is associated with a social and affectionate exchange, as with an evening among friends or in the privacy of his home, after a meal, a dessert, as self-gratification.
- the passionate ones, that is, those with a sort of primary defined passion, not organised into codes and legitimate reasons. There is no rational explanation to the consumption, but it is regulated by impulses that are associated with gluttony and whim, and are therefore not associable with any particular time of the day.
- the sporty ones, that is, those involved in jobs with high energy demands. Chocolate is seen as a food supplement and is consumed when it is considered that energy to burn is needed or to restore energy after physical activity.

Based on all of this it emerges that the different individual consumers of chocolate attribute various significances to chocolate, not classifiable definitively as correct or incorrect.

PACKAGING

The chocolate bars are contained in packaging that above all satisfies a series of functional requirements including: keeping the product in the best way possible by protecting it from light, humidity and heat (that could compromise its organoleptic or aesthetic qualities with phenomena of blossoming of the sugars and cocoa butter) and ease its consumption through straightforward packaging, easily open and possibly re-sealable.

In addition to the indispensable functional requirements, packaging should also satisfy a series of informative requirements (sales classification, cocoa content, name and location of the producer, ingredients, best-before date, weight, cocoa provenance, nutritional values and conservation methods) to increase the user's knowledge of the product and environmental requirements (minimisation of resources and disposal of packaging) to deal with the environmental question, also of topical interest nowadays in the food packaging context (Allione, De Giorgi, Lerma and Petrucci, 2011).

In the specific case of chocolate bars, it is possible to identify, as a result of analyses carried out on 40 different products on the market, three principal packaging types, characterised by different forms and materials:

- box, generally made of cardboard and easily re-sealable in the majority of cases.
- flow pack, a packaging, made of plastic film or multilayers, that is sealed at the two ends. This airtight packaging in general, cannot be resealed.
- wrapper, packaging obtained by means of a sheet of paper, which, by using folds, wraps the chocolate bar, without resealing it in an airtight manner. In certain cases the wrapper can be the primary packaging (in aluminium, polypropylene or paper) of the box or other types, or may be a double wrapper, that is, with a second layer generally made of paper (Bucchiatti and Ciravegna, 2009).

THE BAR

From the analysis carried on the bars easily found on the market in addition to their classification based on form, portion, breaking up and taste, it is possible to outline an additional and innovative method of classification based on their various presentation forms.

Classification that is not limited to the simple distinction between simple and complex form (composed of the typical squares easily divisible and separable or left to the creativity of the creator), but which was extended by comparing the different structures of the bars with the presentation forms of traditional materials (metals, woods, composites, etc.) and the related production processes, such as fusions, mixes (composite, sandwich boards, mouldings and foams).

Each presentation form is determined firstly by the component ingredients, and on many occasions it will be determined by a combination of two or more of these (Figure 2).

Fusion

Fusion is a process that allows melted material to be cast inside a mould.

Carried out in this context it can be compared to the chocolate tempered in the basic tastes (white, milk

and plain) and subsequently cast into moulds in the complex or less complex form.

Composite

The composite is a material composed of various elements joined by means of a binding substance. In the world of chocolate the binder is composed of the three base tastes (white, milk and dark), to which are then added the elements, which, depending on size, will define four different granulometries of the mix:

- very fine, characterised by the insertion into the matrix of elements that are so fine as not to be detected in a tactile manner by the palate or only to a minimal degree. These ingredients can be: aniseed, coffee, cinnamon, cardamom, liquorice, mint, nutmeg, paprika, white pepper, black pepper, pink pepper, chilli pepper, vanilla, ginger, etc.;
- fine, presents fine elements detectable, if only to a minimal degree, by the palate, such as for example: orange salt, tealeaves, bean grains, cane sugar, caster sugar, etc.;
- medium, composed of elements of a dimension such as to require chewing, even if minimal:

caramel, cereals, nuts (cashew nuts, peanuts, almonds, hazelnut, walnuts, pine nuts, pistachios), biscuit chips, fruit peel, etc.;

- large, distinguishable by the presence of large elements, such as to require a chewing, by necessity: biscuit, candied fruit, caramel, cereals, nuts (cashew nuts, peanuts, almonds, hazelnuts, walnuts, pine nuts, pistachios) etc.

As a result of the addition of the elements, the pastry obtained will be blended and subsequently poured into the special moulds.

Sandwich board

By sandwich board is intended a material consisting of two skins or sides separated by a core.

In the world of chocolate bars this presentation form is distinguishable each time a layering is present within the chocolate. The skins are created through the fusion process, in the three base chocolates (white, milk and dark), while the in-between layer (core) may have a different consistency depending on the component ingredients: biscuit, milk, marzipan, stracciatella, wafer, yogurt, etc.

base chocolate

fusion

is a process that allows melted material to be cast inside a mould

composite

is a material composed of various elements joined by means of a binding substance

sandwich board

is a material composed of two skins separated by a core

moulding

is a process that enables plastic material to be injected inside a mould

foam

is a material composed for the most part of its volume of air

Figure 2. Classification of chocolate bar presentation forms

Moulding

Moulding is a process that enables plastic material to be injected inside a mould. The parallel with the world of chocolate bars is possible thanks to those bars with a structure such as to appear as many chocolates combined. In this case the mould is represented by frames created through the fusion process of the base tastes (white, milk and plain), into which the filling will be injected, which may be distinguished as follows:

- liquid, such as, for example, coffee, liqueurs and wines;
- semi-solid, such as jams and mousses.

Foam

Foam is defined as a material, composed for the most part, of its volume of air. It is possible to draw a parallel with the world of chocolate bars, by identifying a new addition to the sector, that is, aerated chocolate, such as a foam. This type of chocolate is obtained by means of a physical process requiring the use of certain gases. Current production is limited to white, milk and plain tastes.

Adopting this methods of classification (Figure 2), in addition to identifying new design approach, as we will see in subsequent paragraphs, it is also possible to identify a potential method of classification of the chocolate-material that could be used within a cupboard section of the material library.

INTERACTIONS BETWEEN THE PROTAGONISTS

Once the protagonists of the interaction were investigated, the study moved on to the analysis of the real interaction that takes places between the three players involved.

A first action is identified in the opening and/or closing of the bar's packaging, focusing on the user-packaging relationship. A second action is identifiable in the consumption of the bar, highlighting the bar-user relationship, by a sensory-tasting experience. Interactions triggered by the structures and materials that make up the packaging, which carries out the function of mediator between consumer and bar (Bozzola, 2011).

OPENING AND CLOSING

The first interaction between the user and the chocolate bar is the opening of the packaging and eventually its closing.

This occurs thanks to the concept of affordance (Norman, 1997), or rather, that combination of actions that an object "invites" to be carried out on itself. This concept neither belongs to the subject itself nor to its consumer, but is created by the relationship that is established between them. Therefore, the affordance will be higher, the use of an object, in this case of a packaging, will be more automatic and intuitive.

Opening

By an objective analysis of the opening action, it is possible to identify two opening ways with the use of an instrument, as in the case of some flow packs that are strongly sealed and can be open only by using scissor, or without an instrument.

In the second case, that is, in the case in which the use of a utensil is not required, it is possible to identify a further distinction between: opening in the presence of invitations or without, dictated by the consumer's experience.

Specifically, in the first case, opening with invitations, it is possible to identify four types of invitations (Figure 3):

- invitations to remove, there is a type of "place" on the packaging in which it is possible to place the thumb and through the use of the remaining fingers, you can get to the opening to remove the flap;
- invitations to tear off, the packaging presents places-tabs with broken lines that suggest to the user/consumer to open the bar by means of the removal by tearing these parts;
- graphical invitation, in certain cases, on the packaging there is writing or arrows or, in general, graphical indications suggesting to the user the exact point at which to complete the opening;
- invitations to "release", in this case, the packaging is closed by means of the physical connection of its two ends, having a structure such as to allow them to be joined.

In the second case, on the other hand, of opening without invitations, it is possible to identify five modalities of opening (Figure 3):

- **unsoldering:** this opening method is used in packaging with a flow park structure, in which closing is created by a welding of the material;
- **removing the tab:** this type of opening is very similar to a method of opening with invitations (invitations to remove) and is present in packaging with a box structure. In this case, unlike the opening mentioned above, there is no place for the finger, but, thanks to his own experience, the user will manage to guess the method of opening;
- **peeling off,** involves a very simple opening regarding packaging with a wrapper structure;
- **tearing off,** involves a very simple opening that occurs with aluminium packaging;
- **unwrapping:** is a very rare type of opening, consisting of unwrapping the bar almost like a gift. In general, the opening action can take place on the front, side or back of the packaging itself, requiring the presence of an aid or not.

Opening

Figure 3. Opening systems

Closing

In the same way, by analysing, the opposite action of opening, the closing, it is possible to identify three different modalities of re-sealability (Figure 4):

- **induced:** the structure itself of the packaging suggests the method of closing the packaging to the user/consumer, and is generally present in packaging made of cases and boxes.
- **indicated:** some packaging presents graphical indications, such as writing or drawings, that indicate and explain the method of closing.

- **do-it-yourself,** involves a type of re-sealability that is born of the experience of the user-consumer and may require the input or not of new material.

Despite the bars being rarely single portion, the re-sealability of their packaging often tends not to be a widespread characteristic, and if present it is not always so easy and immediate. Furthermore, in many cases, then, if an incorrect opening occurs, the closing even if provided for in the packaging design, may fail (Ceppa, Fassio and Marino, 2008).

Closing

Figure 4. Closing Systems

CONSUMPTION

The second analysed action is the moment of consumption during which the interaction between consumer and chocolate bar occurs and the user's real tasting-sensory exploration starts (De Nardo, 2009).

It is possible to identify three sequential interactions that may occur during consumption and are dictated both by the characteristics of the chocolate itself and by the choice of the user-consumer, while influencing the sensory perception of the food being consumed. The first interaction consists of the first approach to the bar, when the user-consumer prepares to consume it, to eat it, and concludes with an action of choice between breaking off or biting, according to determined characteristics.

The second interaction follows the first one by necessity and may lead the user to choosing to bite the piece of chocolate or melt it in the mouth. Although the first two are necessary to start and eat the bar, the third interaction, which consists of licking the fingers may not be carried out by all user-consumers, since is not pleasing to the consumer or simply not necessary. Whatever the choice of the

user-consumer, this will substantially influence the perception of the chocolate bar product being enjoyed.

First interaction: breaking off

Breaking off is an interaction that the consumer usually adopts at the moment in which he approaches a multi-portion bar (Figure 5). Indeed, the user can choose *how* to break off the bar, by using a utensil or by using his hands. In the first case the user-consumer will not soil himself, while, in the second case there is the possibility that the body heat will melt the outer layer of the chocolate, which will therefore soil the consumer's fingers. As regards breaking off by means of the use of a utensil, the action may be carried out both with a bar that possesses invitations and with one characterized by a more refined form, and therefore without invitations. In the case of breaking off with the hands, two types of breaking off may occur, regular and irregular.

The first possibility will take place in the presence of a bar with invitations, which will be conceived in an appropriate way to the type of chocolate; the second, on the other hand, results from the approach to bars without invitations.

Breaking off is an action that may be carried out not only with multi-portion bars, but also with single portion bars, in the case in which the consumer wishes to share or simply taste the chocolate bar: indeed, in the most common cases, the biting interaction takes place.

First interaction: biting

Biting is an activity that takes place in the presence of a single portion bar, in so far as the user/consumer will proceed with difficulty to bite a multi-portion bar that can be shared or keep for brief periods and subsequent tastings. In this case also the user can choose how to break off the bar, while soiling the hands or not (Figure 5).

Indeed, the consumer may avail the possibility, offered by certain types of packaging, of eating the chocolate without having direct contact with the hands. The user may bite any type of bar with or without invitations. In the first case it is imagined that the consumer is helped or better directed towards a determined point, the point at which to carry out the

breaking off. In the second case, on the other hand, the user himself will decide the point at which to bite. As regards the biting interaction, it can be stated that in certain cases this action can follow the breaking off. Sometimes, indeed, it is possible that, by breaking off a multi-portion bar, a piece too big to be completely inserted in the mouth is obtained; therefore, in this case, the user-consumer will proceed to bite the chocolate.

First interaction

Figure 3. First Interaction: breaking off and biting

Second interaction: chewing

The chewing interaction represents an action that usually follows that of *biting* (Figure 6).

The user-consumer, indeed, having bitten the chocolate, will continue the interaction by chewing; in certain cases, it involves a journey almost completely unconscious. The consumer carries out this type of activity with any type of chocolate, from chocolate in pieces to the classic one, from the liquid filling to the soft filling, perceiving, however, different sensations. It is important to underline that, once chewing the chocolate is finished, the melting action comes into play, since, in general, traces of the “food of the gods” remain on the tongue and in the mouth and are “removed” through melting.

Second interaction: melting in the mouth

Melting in the mouth is the action that the user-consumer carries out at the moment when he wants the chocolate to have itself eaten (Figure 6).

The chocolate has a melting temperature much less than the one encountered inside our mouth therefore it is possible to state that in the *melting in the mouth* it is the chocolate having itself eaten, rather than the user-consumer eating it. Usually, it is thought that this action is dedicated to a classic chocolate only, but there are users that also choose to melt in the mouth types of chocolate with pieces, in this way, leading to

the isolation of the elements added to the chocolate, such as hazelnuts, chocolate chips, puffed rice, which must be chewed.

Second interaction

Figure 4 - Second Interaction: chewing and melting in the mouth

Third interaction: licking the fingers

It is the activity that enables the completion of the journey initiated. It involves an action the user-consumer can carry out to clean the hands or out of gluttony.

The user-consumers decide on one type of approach rather than the other also based on their gluttony, indeed, as a famous advertisement states “if you don’t lick your fingers you only enjoy by half”.

DESIGNING STARTING WITH THE INTERACTION

Once the analysis of the interaction with the chocolate bar is completed it is possible to make certain observations. The design process, currently used by the food designer, generally has as the initial point the taste of the chocolate bar to be created.

From the analysis carried out, in parallel with the search for a new taste, the design journey that leads to the creation of a new chocolate bar could also take into consideration the user-bar interactions, thus outlining a new design approach.

Indeed, from the parallel study of the consumption ways (breaking off and biting for the first interaction, chewing and *melting in the mouth* for the second, and licking the fingers for the third interaction), and from the analysis of the presentation forms of the chocolate bars (fusions, mixes, sandwich boards, mouldings, foams), it may be noted how it is possible, by means of an overlapping of the results obtained, to develop an innovative design system, that allows bars to be created that are capable of improving the sensory sensation when a bar is tasted.

The objective of this new design system, an instrument for the food designer and planners, is that of starting the design of the desired interaction that the user will develop with the bar. This would enable chocolate bars with characteristics (presentation forms, ingredients, and packaging) that are more consistent for the specific consumption modalities. The system consists of three large areas that correspond to the consumption modalities, the presentation form of the bar and the packaging (Figure 7).

The first element, starting point of the new design system, is given by the consumption methods (first interaction: regular or irregular *breaking off* and *biting*; second interaction: *chewing* and *melting in the mouth*;

Designing from the interaction

Figure 5. Methodological approach to the food designing by using the interaction analysis

third interaction: *licking the fingers*), that individually come into play.

The presentation forms (fusions, mixes, sandwich boards, mouldings and foams), constitute the second element, closely connected to the consumption methods, in how it is composed.

The third element, the packaging, refers to the portion of the bar (single or multi-portion, to the opening (integrated with consumption) and closing (resalable or non-re-sealable) and to the packaging structures (box, flow pack and wrapper).

The areas related to the presentation forms and the packaging are strongly influenced by the consumption methods, particularly by the first interaction, which determines, specifically, the principal characteristics of the packaging.

At the moment in which the attention focuses on the second and third interaction, the third element (packaging) will be abandoned, in so far as it is like a zoom were created inside the mouth of the consumer.

CONCLUSIONS

Currently, the design method has the taste of the bar as its starting point, and it leads the designer to creating formats and presentation forms that, often, pay little attention to the methods with which the end user will approach the bar.

The system presented (Figure 8 – 9) is put forward as an instrument for designers who, in addition to searching for the taste of the product, consider the interaction with the user-consumer to be central: the user-consumer is at the centre of the project (Germak, 2008), keystone of design choices, aimed at the creation of a new chocolate design, a new bar.

For example (Figure 8), if the designer wants to project a chocolate bar, that should be biting, he can choose between different presentation forms (fusion, foam, composite, etc); moreover he can aim the project of the packaging into the selection for a single portion packaging, not re-sealability, whose structure should be a flow a pack or a wrapped packaging.

On the other side (Figure 9), if the designer choose to start from the second interaction, such as chewing, he can chooses the chocolate presentation form that should not be fusion or with a composite very fine and the packaging should follow these choices.

The planner-food designer, by adopting the proposed design methodology, will be able to analyse in an

optimal manner all the parameters that should be involved in the chosen consumption modalities (biting or breaking off? chewing or melting in the mouth? licking the fingers?), while considering various factors, such as for example the times and places of consumption, the dimensions of the mouth, etc. in order to define portions, thicknesses, of the “good” bar, obtained from the optimal mix of ingredients, format, taste and packaging.

Therefore, this system (Figure 8 – 9) brings about an innovation of the chocolate design, extendable hypothetically to other food products designed by designers.

Furthermore, the information necessary for the use of the instrument, related to the presentation forms of the material-chocolate, to the consumption methods and most suitable packaging types, could be useful to planners, food designers who wish to design not only the food, but “for” the food (from the packaging to the instruments for consuming the food).

The first possible places of sharing are the material libraries (Lucibello, 2006; Ferrara and Lucibello, 2009), physical or virtual places in which technical information on broad ranges of materials are gathered and made available, relating, in particular, to the world of architecture design, fashion and industrial production in general.

Within the material libraries a cupboard section may be set up, dedicated to the world of materials-foods, of which to analyse presentation forms, production processes, technical and expressive qualities, consumption methods and also, as a consequence, the types of packaging most suited to them. In this way the food will be considered to all intents and purposes a material, which, designers, not just as food designers, master chocolate manufacturers and chefs, get to know.

First interaction: regular breaking off

First interaction: irregular breaking off

First interaction: biting

highly recommended (dark brown) average recommended (white) poorly recommended (diagonal lines)

Figure 6. Methodological approach of Designing by interaction analysis: First interaction

Second interaction: chewing

Second interaction: melting in the mouth

Third interaction: licking the fingers

highly recommended (solid dark brown) average recommended (diagonal lines) poorly recommended (cross-hatch)

Figure 7. Methodological approach of Designing by interaction analysis: Second and Third interactions

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